

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES
AS A FUNCTION OF MATRIX MODULUS OF ELASTICITY
AND COMPONENT WALL THICKNESS

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ABSTRACT

Variations in compressive strength as a function of matrix modulus of elasticity and component wall thickness are considered for continuous unidirectional fiber reinforced composite materials. Microbuckling in transversely supported fibers is presented as the failure mechanism. Short prismatic columns and three-point flexure samples are utilized as representative composite material components. An energy method is employed to calculate component compressive strength at fiber microbuckle loads. Finite element analysis methods utilizing fiber and resin properties are employed to evaluate composite mechanical properties and transverse stiffness. Microbuckling stresses for fiber reinforced three-point flexure samples of varying thicknesses and resin moduli are predicted and compared with experimental results. Reasonable correlation is observed, including reduction in ultimate strength with increasing wall thickness and decreasing resin modulus.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In the development of primary and secondary continuous fiber reinforced composite material components, the first requirement is structural integrity. In order to satisfy this requirement, composite material components must be designed so that the internal stress fields will always be within structural failure limits for tensile, shear, and compressive stresses. Failure levels for tensile and shear stresses in fiber reinforced composites are reasonably well understood; thus, they do not pose significant problems for the experienced developer. However, the same cannot be said for compressive stresses. There are many issues which enter into the analysis of compressive failure in composites. Of the first order is the introduction of microbuckling as an additional failure mode. From the several theories which attempt to characterize microbuckling, it appears that this failure mode is a function of resin properties, fiber properties, fiber volume fraction, and component geometry. Of higher order are the effects of kinking, initial fiber waviness, void content, broken fibers, fiber alignment, fiber resin interface, water and other liquid saturation,

cosmic ray impingement, and resin strain to failure. All of these issues contribute in some negative way to compressive strength - leading to failures at load levels significantly below that which is generally predicted with existing analysis tools.

While it is generally accepted that microbuckling is a prime mover in the compressive failure of continuous fiber reinforced composite material components, most developers either ignore the phenomenon or design around it. Those who ignore it, and they make up the significant majority of developers, are usually surprised with low-level failures following first or second article fabrication. The primary reasons for this lack of consideration is the absence of the necessary analytical tools and the understanding of the physics of the phenomenon. It is the thrust of this paper to expose the physics of fiber microbuckling as it is related to resin modulus and component wall thickness; and to present the first step in the development of an analytical tool which will enable the prediction of the onset of fiber microbuckling during compressive load buildup.

2.0 STRENGTH TESTS AND ANALYSIS

For edification with respect to fiber microbuckling physics, two sets of strength tests were conducted with varying resin moduli and different sample wall thicknesses. One involved axial compression to failure of short prismatic columns; and the other, transverse mid-span loading to failure of simply supported beams. See figures (1) and (2). Experimental results are presented, and comparisons to an energy based analysis for estimating in-phase fiber microbuckling are made. See figure (3).

Figure 1. Unidirectional Continuous Fiber Reinforced Composite Subjected to Compressive Loading

Figure 2. Simply Supported Beam with Transverse Mid-Span Load

Figure 3. Microbuckling under Compressive Loading

2.1 Column and Flexure Strength Tests For the first test group, a set of ASTM style compression tests, the materials utilized for the composite samples were S2 fiberglass and four mixtures of Union Carbide's ERL 4205 and Shell's Epon 828 epoxy resins. The four resin mixtures provided a range in matrix modulus of elasticity from 410 KSI to 620 KSI, in 70 KSI increments. The gage length and width of all samples were nominally 0.5 inches. The test samples in each resin bin were fabricated in two wall thicknesses, 0.1 inch and 0.2 inches nominally with all reinforcing fibers continuous and unidirectional - making a set of eight test sample bins. The average fiber volume fraction was 64%, and it ranged from 60.3% to 69%. The average void content was 2%, and it ranged from 0.5% to 3.5%.

Each sample was compressively loaded as a column in an ASTM style fixture. All samples were loaded to failure. Some fractured in the test gage region at the interface of the fixture grip and the sample outer layer. For others, the failure was characterized as a brooming at the end of the column due to grip slippage. Those that failed in brooming did so at compressive strengths higher than those that failed in the test gage region.

Data reduction for these tests was accomplished by a smeared properties column compressive strength analysis. An adjustment was made for fiber content. All test results were adjusted to the average fiber volume content by multiplying the ultimate stress calculated by a simple ratio of 64% to actual fiber volume content. No compensation was made for void content because there is no comprehensive data available with respect to the effects of void content. Additionally the void contents for the eight sample bins did not vary significantly, nor were they very large. The compressive strength test data, including averaged and adjusted stresses, are provided in tables (1a) and (1b) and figure (4).

The second test group was a set of three-point flexure tests. The samples which made up the sample bins were materially and geometrically equivalent to the compression test samples. However, since they were to be used in flexure tests, the test lengths were longer than the compression test gage lengths. For the 0.1 inch deep beam, the test length was 3.0 inches. For the 0.2 inch deep beam, the test length was 4.5 inches.

Each sample was loaded to failure with a line load at center span. All samples failed in compression. All failed at mid-span where failure was expected, since that was the location of maximum bending moment; thus, maximum bending stress.

Data reduction was accomplished by a smeared properties bending analysis. Fiber content was adjusted to the average fiber volume fraction in the same manner as in the compression tests. A second adjustment was made for large transverse deflections. The large deflections were compensated for by measuring beam deflections during the flexure tests, fitting a curve to the measured deflections, and evaluating the second derivative at mid-beam where simple beam theory held over ranges of one inch or less. For the larger of the two sample thicknesses tested (0.2 inches nominally), there was little difference between data reduction with or without large deflections accounted for. The flexure (compressive) strength test data, including averaged and adjusted stresses, are provided in tables (2a) and (2b) and figure (5).

SAMPLE POPULATION	4	5	5	8
RESIN MODULUS (KSI)	410	480	550	620
SAMPLE GAGE LENGTH (IN)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
SAMPLE WIDTH (IN)	0.508	0.506	0.508	0.510
WALL THICKNESS (IN)	0.104	0.103	0.093	0.085
FIBER VOLUME (%)	60.3	63.6	65.5	65.0
VOID CONTENT (%)	1.09	1.44	2.44	2.36
FAILURE LOAD (LBS)	8695	9672	9070	9796
FAILURE STRESS (KSI)	153	185	193	226
FAIL STRESS/ $V_f=64\%$ (KSI)	162	186	188	223

Table 1a. S2 Fiberglass/Epoxy Resin Compression Tests - Averaged Data for 0.1 Inch Nominal Sample Thickness

SAMPLE POPULATION	5	5	5	5
RESIN MODULUS (KSI)	410	480	550	620
SAMPLE GAGE LENGTH (IN)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
SAMPLE WIDTH (IN)	0.503	0.508	0.507	0.505
WALL THICKNESS (IN)	0.186	0.204	0.193	0.175
FIBER VOLUME (%)	60.3	61.7	66.7	69
VOID CONTENT (%)	1.61	2.32	1.55	N/A
FAILURE LOAD (LBS)	12144	12274	15126	15620
FAILURE STRESS (KSI)	129	118	155	177
FAIL STRESS/ $V_f=64\%$ (KSI)	137	122	149	164

Table 1b. S2 Fiberglass/Epoxy Resin Compression Tests - Averaged Data for 0.2 Inch Nominal Sample Thickness

Figure 4. Unidirectional S2 Fiberglass/Epoxy Resin Compression Test Results as a Function of Resin Modulus - Normalized for 64% Fiber Volume Fraction

SAMPLE POPULATION	3	3	3	3
RESIN MODULUS (KSI)	410	480	550	620
SAMPLE GAGE LNGTH (IN)	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
SAMPLE WIDTH (IN)	0.509	0.506	0.507	0.504
WALL THICKNESS (IN)	0.103	0.102	0.095	0.085
FIBER VOLUME (%)	60.3	63.6	65.5	65
VOID CONTENT (%)	1.07	1.44	2.44	2.36
FAILURE LOAD (LBS)	211	241	239	207
FAILURE STRESS (KSI)	207	240	276	295
FAIL STRESS/Vf=64% (KSI)	220	242	270	291

Table 2a. S2 Fiberglass/Epoxy Resin Three-Point Flexure Tests - Averaged Data for 0.1 Inch Nominal Sample Thickness

SAMPLE POPULATION	3	3	3	3
RESIN MODULUS (KSI)	410	480	550	620
SAMPLE GAGE LNGTH (IN)	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
SAMPLE WIDTH (IN)	0.507	0.504	0.510	0.508
WALL THICKNESS (IN)	0.187	0.204	0.191	0.175
FIBER VOLUME (%)	60.3	61.7	66.7	69
VOID CONTENT (%)	1.61	2.32	1.55	N/A
FAILURE LOAD (LBS)	404	527	530	515
FAILURE STRESS (KSI)	154	169	192	227
FAIL STRESS/Vf=64% (KSI)	164	177	186	211

Table 2b. S2 Fiberglass/Epoxy Resin Three-Point Flexure Tests - Averaged Data for 0.2 Inch Nominal Sample Thickness

Figure 5. Unidirectional S2 Fiberglass/Epoxy Resin Three-Point Flexure Test Data as a Function of Resin Modulus - Normalized for 64% Fiber Volume Fraction

2.2 In-Phase Microbuckling Analysis An energy based fiber microbuckling analysis was performed with respect to the three-point flexure test samples. See references [1] and [2] for the development of a strain energy approach for the prediction of buckling of a bar on an elastic foundation; and for the application of this approach to the in-phase microbuckling of reinforcing fibers in a polymer matrix. From reference [2],

$$P_{Cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_f I_f}{L^2} \left[n^2 + \frac{BL^4}{n^2 \pi^4 E_f I_f} \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$S_{Cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_f I_f}{A_f L^2} \left[n^2 + \frac{BL^4}{n^2 \pi^4 E_f I_f} \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

where S_{Cr} is the ultimate composite compressive stress; V_f is composite fiber volume fraction; E_f is fiber elasticity modulus; I_f is fiber area moment of inertia; A_f is fiber cross-sectional area; L is length of test sample; n is the number of microbuckle half-waves; and B is the foundation stiffness per unit length.

To predict the minimum compressive stresses at which the various three-point flexure test samples will fail, we have to evaluate B and minimize S_{Cr} with respect to n in equation (2). In evaluating B , the first step is to establish the elastic foundation's transverse modulus of elasticity, E_c . This is accomplished by utilizing a finite element model of a fiber in a matrix with the appropriate fiber volume fraction and matrix and fiber mechanical properties. See figure (6) for a graphic representation of the model, load, and constraint format.

The second step is to evaluate B from a finite element model of a portion of the three-point flexure sample. See figure (7). In this model, E_c is the basic composite mechanical property and B is evaluated from the relative displacements of the upper and lower surfaces of the test sample.

With B evaluated, we are left with calculating the minimum critical stresses from equation (2). See figure (8) for a graphic representation of calculations for S_{Cr} and comparisons with three-point flexure experimental results presented in tables (2a) and (2b).

Figure 6. Finite Element Model for a Fiber Encased in an Epoxy Matrix

Figure 7. Finite Element Model of a Portion of a Typical Three-Point Flexure Test Sample with Transverse Loading

Figure 8. Unidirectional S2 Fiberglass/Epoxy Resin Three-Point Flexure Test Data Compared to Fiber Microbuckle Analysis - Normalized for 64% Fiber Volume Fraction

3.0 CONCLUDING REMARKS

For equivalent sample thicknesses and resin moduli, the three-point flexure test samples, as compared to the compressive test samples, achieved consistently higher critical compressive stress levels. This difference can be attributed to the influence of the test fixture. In the compression tests, the fixture grips constrained the test samples, giving rise to elevated local compressive stresses. A finite element based analysis provided insight into these raised stresses.

The overall results of the column and flexure tests indicate that there is a relationship between compressive strength and resin elastic modulus as well as sample wall thickness. The indications are that there is a fall-off in compressive strength with respect to reduction in resin modulus, as well as with increase in test sample wall thickness. Camponeschi's [5] and Augl's [6] observations support the indication of a relationship between compressive strength and compression sample wall thickness.

These observations support the assumption that the basic failure mode for continuous fiber reinforced polymer matrices under compressive loading is characterized by microbuckling in the reinforcing fibers. The microbuckling analysis performed to predict failure in the three-point flexure samples followed the trend of the test data except for a small bias. The bias observed is most likely due to knockdown factors inherent in the test samples. This analysis was an extension of the developments of Rosen [3] and Hahn and Williams [4].

4.0 REFERENCES

1. Timoshenko, S. P. and Gere, J. M., THEORY OF ELASTIC STABILITY, Second Edition, McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc, 1961
2. Spicola, F. C. and Dubois, N. J., AN ALGORITHM FOR THE ANALYSIS OF CRITICAL STRESSES IN CONTINUOUS FILAMENT REINFORCED FLAT PLATES SUBJECTED TO UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPRESSIVE LOADING, Eighth International Conference on Composite Materials Proceedings, Society for the Advancement of Material and Processing Engineering (SAMPE), et al, July 1991.
3. Rosen, B. W., MECHANICS OF COMPOSITE STRENGTHENING, Fiber Composite Materials, American Society for Metals, 1965, pp 37-75
4. Hahn, T. H. and Williams, J. G., COMPRESSION FAILURE MECHANISMS IN UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES, Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Seventh Conference), ASTM STP 893, J. M. Whitney, Ed., American Society for Testing Materials, Philadelphia, 1986, pp. 115-139.
5. Camponeschi, E. T., COMPRESSION TESTING OF THICK SECTION COMPOSITE MATERIALS, David Taylor Research Center Report # DTRC SME-89-73, Oct 1989.
6. Augl, J. M., STRESS RUPTURE OF COMPOSITES IN COMPRESSION, Naval Surface Warfare Center Presentation, April 2, 1991